

The Dieckmann-Komppa Reaction of Diethyl Thiodiacetate and Diethyl Oxalate

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This communication deals with certain abnormalities observed in the Dieckmann-Komppa reaction of diethyl thiodiacetate and diethyl oxalate under different experimental conditions.

The Dieckmann-Komppa reaction of diesters and oxalic esters is a Claisen condensation followed by a Dieckmann cyclisation, leading to cycloalkane-dione diesters. Thorpe *et. al.*¹ showed the formation of diethyl α -keto β -carbethoxy adipate as an intermediate in the reaction of diethyl glutarate, and suggested the above generalised sequence.

Certain abnormalities in the Dieckmann cyclisation have been noted earlier^{2,3,4}, the course of the reaction being dependant upon the experimental conditions. Similar observations are noted in the Dieckmann-Komppa reaction of diethyl thiodiacetate (I) and diethyl oxalate (II) leading to 2,5-dicarbethoxy-3, 4-dihydroxy thiophene(V)⁵, the dienol form of the cyclic dione (IV).

In ethanolic sodium ethoxide the reaction gave nearly 80% yield of the thiophene, while with powdered sodium in benzene, the yield of the thiophene (V), dropped to 30%. In the latter case, the intermediate pyruvate (III) was isolated, which underwent facile ring closure with ethanolic sodium ethoxide to the thiophene (V). The mechanism of the formation of the ester (III) will proceed in a manner analogous to the acetoacetic ester synthesis^{3,6}, the reaction can then proceed as follows:

1. F. Dickens, G. A. R. Kon and J. F. Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1496.
2. R. B. Woodward and R. H. Eastman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2229.
3. D. K. Banerjee, J. Dutta, and G. Bagavant, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sciences*, 1957, 46 A, 80.
4. G. B. Kline, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 2251.
5. O. Hinsberg, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 901.
6. R. I. Reed and M. B. Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2148.

In refluxing alcoholic sodium ethoxide the system is under equilibrating conditions³. Apart from the normal resonance stabilisation of the enolate synion (IVa), the delocalisation in the aromatic structure of the enolate dianion (IVb) would greatly stabilise the cyclic system and lead to a high yield of the thiophene (V), in the equilibrium mixture. It was found that attempted fission of the thiophene (V), with a trace of sodium ethoxide in ethanol failed, the starting material was recovered (95%); indicating the far lesser basicity of the enolate (IVa, IVb) over either the synion (IIIa) or the ethoxide ion.

With sodium in refluxing benzene, there is very little availability of the alkoxide ion; and in steps 1 and 2, the small quantity of the existing ethoxide ion will preferably extract the more acidic methine hydrogen to form the stabler enolate synion (IIIa) (step 1), rather than the methylene hydrogen to form the carbanion (IIIb) (step 2). The subsequent reactions are thus repressed leading to a low yield of the thiophene (V). It was found that when the pyruvate (III) was treated with sodium dust in benzene, the sodium salt of the enolate immediately separated, and on working up, the starting material was recovered.

The formation of a bianion (IIIc) directly from (IIIa) without going through (III) is considered energetically unlikely³, further the carbonyl activity will be highly diminished for cyclisation.

When the condensation is effected at 0° with alcoholic free sodium ethoxide in anhydrous ether, a good yield of the pyruvate (III) is obtained, and there is negligible formation of the thiophene.

The above explanations support the unusual observation that in this reaction, an alcoholic medium gives a better yield than an inert medium, for it is generally noted that in an acetoacetic ester synthesis, an alcoholic medium lessens the yield due to aiding the reversibility in the final step, by mass effect of the ethanol.⁷

EXPERIMENTAL

Diethyl Thiodiacetate: Thiodiacetic acid was prepared in 66% yield by modification of the procedure of Dey and Dutt⁸. Esterification with azeotropic removal of water gave diethyl thiodiacetate b.p. 267-68° (lit.⁹ b.p. 267-68°) in 70% yield.

Condensation of Diethyl Thiodiacetate and Diethyl Oxalate in presence of Alcoholic Sodium Ethoxide: To a refluxing solution of alcoholic sodium ethoxide (0.22 mole), prepared from sodium (5.0 g.) and absolute ethanol (75 ml.), was slowly added a mixture of diethyl oxalate (14.6 g., 0.1 mole), diethyl thiodiacetate (20.6 g., 0.1 mole) and thiophene free dry benzene (25 ml.) under anhydrous conditions, over 15 min., and then the reaction mixture refluxed for 2.5 hr., cooled to 0°, diluted with benzene and filtered. The precipitate on acidification to congo red with ice-cold 6N-hydrochloric acid deposited 2,5-dicarbethoxy-3,4-dihydroxy thiophene (20.0 g., m.p. 131°, lit.⁵ m.p. 134°, crystallised from ethanol), yield 77%.

Ice-cold water (200 ml.) was added to the filtrate, the aqueous phase was washed with benzene to remove the neutral starting materials and then acidified to congo red with ice-cold 6N-hydrochloric acid, and extracted with benzene (2 × 100 ml.). The benzene phase was washed with ice-cold brine, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed when the pyruvate (III) (2.0 g.) was obtained. This gave an intense colour with ferric chloride and decomposed on distillation.

Condensation of Diethyl Thiodiacetate and Diethyl Oxalate with Sodium in refluxing Benzene: To a refluxing suspension of powdered sodium (5.0 g., 0.22 mole) in thiophene free dry benzene (75 ml.) was gradually added a mixture of diethyl oxalate (14.6 g., 0.1 mole), diethyl thiodiacetate (20.6 g., 0.1 mole) and benzene (25 ml.) over 15 min. under anhydrous conditions. (A few drops of absolute ethanol were added to initiate the reaction.) The evolution of hydrogen ceased after 1 hr., the reaction mixture was kept under reflux for a further 1 hr., then cooled to 0°, and worked up as in the above experiment when it gave 2,5-dicarbethoxy-3,4-dihydroxy thiophene (8.0 g., 31% yield), and diethyl α -ethoxyoxalylthiodiacetate (III) (17.0 g., 55% yield).

Dieckmann Cyclisation of Diethyl α -Ethoxyoxalylthiodiacetate (III) with Alcoholic Sodium Ethoxide: To ethanolic sodium ethoxide from sodium (1.2 g., 0.05 mole) and absolute alcohol (30 ml.), was added diethyl α -ethoxyoxalylthiodiacetate (III) (7.8 g., 0.025

7. C. R. Hauser and B. E. Hudson, 'Organic Reactions' Vol. I, John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, 1942, p. 278.

8. A. N. Dey and S. Dutt, *This Journal*, 1928, 5, 640.

9. M. Heilbron and H. M. Bunbury, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds', Vol. III, Eyre and Spottiswoode Ltd., 15, Bedford Street, Strand, London, W.C. 2, 1943, p. 751.

mole) in benzene (15 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. under anhydrous conditions, cooled to 0° and the solid mass broken, and acidified to congo red with ice-cold 2N-hydrochloric acid, and extracted with ether (3 × 100 ml.). The combined organic phase was washed with brine, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The residue (6.0 g.) was crystallised from alcohol when the thiophene (V), m.p. 131°, 5.1 g., was obtained.

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